

Review of CoreTrustSeal Applicability to non-Preservation (Trustworthy) Data Services¹

UK Data Service²

Successful applicants for CoreTrustSeal Trustworthy Digital Repository (TDR) certification³, must offer active long term preservation for the data and metadata they hold. But not all data services provide long term preservation. Some of the 16 CoreTrustSeal Requirements⁴ are preservation-specific but many other requirements reflect organisational infrastructure, technology & security, and digital object management criteria that are applicable to any service that stores, creates, curates or provides access to data or metadata.

This brief working paper provides a tabular overview of the CoreTrustSeal⁵ Requirements and how they apply to non-preservation data and metadata services. These services could include storage providers⁶, services that require basic metadata at the point of deposit⁷ but take no longer term responsibility, or data and metadata registries. These services may, or may not, partner with a TDR that provides long term preservation for their data and/or metadata. The alignment options for each Requirement are: 'yes', 'no' or 'partial'.

Some concluding remarks provide a first outline of the functional components of trustworthy data services based on this initial analysis. With the exceptions of "Preservation Plan" and "ReUse" our assessment is that all of the CoreTrustSeal Requirements are applicable to any (meta)data service that seeks to demonstrate trustworthiness to its depositors, funders, users and peers.

This work is part of an ongoing process of planning and engagement with peers⁸ both internal to the UK Data Service and as a part of our contribution to Future Data Services⁹. This is a first step in an internal planning and analysis process by the UK Data Service. It is shared in the interests of transparency and to provide a reference point for some engagement with peers on this topic.

¹ This document <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6865990>

² <https://ukdataservice.ac.uk/>

³ Including the UK Data Archive, lead partner in the UK Data Service

<https://www.data-archive.ac.uk/managing-data/data-preservation-and-trust/trusted-digital-repository/>

⁴ CoreTrustSeal Trustworthy Digital Repositories Requirements 2023-2025 Extended Guidance

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7051096>

⁵ <https://www.coretrustseal.org/>

⁶ E.g. Amazon Web Services (AWS) <https://aws.amazon.com/>

⁷ E.g. Zenodo <https://about.zenodo.org/policies/>

⁸ E.g. Information Architecture For Secure Trustworthy Data Services, presented at IASSIST 2022.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6822236>

⁹ <https://www.ukri.org/what-we-offer/browse-our-areas-of-investment-and-support/future-data-services/>

Version 2.0

This version of the paper has been updated to align with the final approved version of the CoreTrustSeal 2023-2025 Requirements.

The authors would like to gratefully acknowledge the feedback on the original draft from the members of the European Open Science Cloud Association's (EOSC-A¹⁰) Long Term Data Preservation Task Force (LTDP-TF)¹¹, which have informed this revised text and the proposed next stages of work to examine the alignment of data service functions and activities with a wider set of current standards, criteria and requirements.

¹⁰ <https://eosc.eu/>

¹¹ <https://www.eosc.eu/advisory-groups/long-term-data-preservation>

CoreTrustSeal Grouping	CoreTrustSeal Requirements Headings for 2023-25	Applicable to all (meta) data services?	Comments based on UK Data Service internal discussion
Organisational Infrastructure	Mission/Scope (R01)	Yes	Understanding the mission and scope of any service is necessary for it to be assessed. With the exception of the specific CoreTrustSeal reference to 'preservation' being a part of the mission, this is necessary for all services, whether or not they include preservation services.
Organisational Infrastructure	Rights Management (R02)	Yes	Different services may have different levels of rights, obligations, permissions and prohibitions in place. But a rights management framework is necessary for all services that engage with data or metadata.
Organisational Infrastructure	Continuity of Service (R03)	Yes	Continuity, disaster recovery and succession planning are necessary to ensure the sustainability of any service, and to minimise the current and future risks to digital objects.
Organisational Infrastructure	Legal & Ethical (R04)	Yes	Any service should be able to demonstrate that it is aware of and complies with the legal, regulatory and ethical framework that it functions within.
Organisational Infrastructure	Governance & Resources (R05)	Yes	A clear system of governance and sufficient human and financial resources is necessary to deliver any effective and sustainable service.
Organisational Infrastructure	Expertise & Guidance (R06)	Yes	Any service should be able to demonstrate that it has, or has access to, appropriate expertise to operate the service. The types and depth of expertise will of course vary depending on the service.

Digital Object Management	Provenance & Authenticity (R07)	Yes	Any (meta)data service must be able to assert the authenticity and provenance of a digital object it provides access to, even if it does not undertake curation or preservation.
Digital Object Management	Deposit & Appraisal (R08)	Yes	There must be a clear deposit process. Criteria for accepting or rejecting offers (appraisal) must be present even if they are very broad.
Digital Object Management	Preservation Plan (R09)	Partial	A preservation plan <i>may</i> only be required when there is a specific preservation remit for the data service. But, ideally, the value of digital assets should be periodically re-appraised over time. The outcome of a reappraisal may lead to a decision to increase or decrease the level of curation-preservation applied to a digital object. This implies that services that do not provide active long-term preservation should still be 'preservation aware'. This awareness would allow the service to avoid taking actions that could reduce the possibilities of future preservation. A storage-only service that limited deposits to preservation-friendly formats would be an example.
Digital Object Management	Quality Assurance (R10)	Yes	For all services, quality must be assured through measures that assess standards compliance. The level of compliance, including any failures to comply with agreed quality criteria, should be recorded and shared through provenance information.
Digital Object Management	Workflows (R11)	Yes	During the transition from deposit to access, all services must be able to demonstrate that they have sufficiently developed and auditable workflows to ensure complete and consistent management of processes.
Digital Object Management	Discovery & Identification (R12)	Yes	Resource discovery of digital objects' data and metadata is necessary for all services. Unique and persistent identification at an appropriate object level to support standard discovery functions, and potentially to very granular

			levels e.g. datum objects, is a dependency for many other actions.
Digital Object Management	ReUse (R13)	Partial	Though only an active long term preservation service will ensure that (meta)data remain re-usable over time, other types of data service should be 're-use aware'. A storage-only service might restrict deposits to specific file formats or metadata schemas considered to be acceptable for re-use. A service offering a level of curation that falls short of preservation can still choose to set standards or undertake curation actions that ensure reusability at the <i>initial</i> point of access.
Technology & Security	Storage and Integrity (R14)	Yes	Necessary for all services. Ideally described to some community-agreed level covering multiple copies, in multiple locations on multiple media with acceptable integrity and recovery measures in place.
Technology & Security	Technical Infrastructure (R15)	Yes	Necessary for all services. Ideally described to some community-agreed level, covering key components and management approaches.
Technology & Security	Security (R16)	Yes	Necessary for all services. Ideally described to some community-agreed level covering key components and management approaches. Adapted to the sensitivity level and disclosure risk of the (meta)data being held.

Concluding Remarks

In this initial UK Data Service review of the CoreTrustSeal Requirements 2023-25, our assessment is that all of the CoreTrustSeal Requirements are applicable to any data service with the exceptions of Preservation Plan (Requirement 09) and ReUse (R13).

Even in cases where a data service is 'storage only' or offers a sub-preservation level of curation, the activities should ideally be 'preservation-aware' and 're-use aware' to enable a future decision to bring the data and/or metadata of a digital object under formal, active long term preservation.

Diagram: CoreTrustSeal Requirements 2023-25 with Preservation and ReUse highlighted and Access added.

The diagram above presents the CoreTrustSeal Requirements 2023-25, with the Preservation and Reuse requirements highlighted. The UK Data Service has added the Access function as critical to our services. Access is not a separate requirement in CoreTrustSeal though is implied throughout and required as a condition of the Mission (R01).

The functional entities of the OAIS Reference Model¹² are presented in the diagram below. The current UK Data Service functional model¹³ aligns itself with the OAIS, though it specifies a Pre-Ingest (analogous to Deposit and Appraisal in CoreTrustSeal) separately from the Ingest function (which aligns with Quality Assurance).

The UK Data Archive and the UK Data Service comply with a number of standards that are more rigorous than CoreTrustSeal including ISO27001 for Information Security Management. This implies a more specific functional need for data and metadata services to have a policy and evidence framework to manage the link between practice and compliance. The next phase of this work will review a number of other standards, requirements and criteria relevant to repositories and data services with a view to generating a broader set of functions and activities relevant to data and metadata services.

OAIS Reference Model (2012) Functional Entities

¹² Reference Model for an Open Archival Information System (OAIS)

<https://public.ccsds.org/pubs/650x0m2.pdf>

¹³ UK Data Archive Preservation Policy

<https://dam.data-archive.ac.uk/controlled/cd062-preservationpolicy.pdf>